

Mitigating restriction to crop production due to Covid-19 pandemic and climatic uncertainty – A case for irrigation and a novel capillary irrigation system

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Abstract

Assess to food in the right quantity and quality is essential to healthy life, and peaceful co-existence. Crop production is critical to global food security and socioeconomic health. Soil water availability determines cropping season and cycles, and water stress can cause a significant reduction in yield even when other factors affecting crop production are adequate. Nigerian crop production is primarily rainfed and are prone to risk due to rainfall uncertainty. Restriction to movement and input supply due to Covid-19 pandemic further depressed cropping activities and affordable food supply. Irrigation has the potential to extend the growing season and consequently reduce crop production deficit and can also ensure water supply when rainfall is inadequate. In areas where annual rainfall far exceeds annual evapotranspiration, there is still the need for supplementary irrigation for optimum yield. We developed a novel irrigation device based on the principle of capillarity which has been tested and adopted for the cultivation of vegetables. Study indicated between 20.5 and 30.5 increase in yield of amaranth and it's found to be significant ($P < 0.05$). Yields were found to increase significantly even when rainfall was considered normal, underscoring the need for supplementary irrigation in the southern Nigeria. With reduction in the frequency of farm visit for irrigation, particularly during the dry season, the yield advantage and the potential to reduce risk of crop failure in the face of climatic uncertainties, this and other irrigation techniques with comparatively high water used efficiency are suggested.

Keywords: Capillary irrigation, water use efficiency, water application efficiency, *Amaranthus viridis*

Introduction

Threat to food production and socio-economic development:

Increasing food production in the right quantity and quality is considered to be crucial in feeding the world rapidly increasing population. This requires timely and precise management of agricultural inputs (Taugourdeau *et al.*, 2014; Sankaran *et al.*, 2015). Apart from being an important sector to food security, agriculture is also essential in providing employment opportunities to rural population (Iglesias and Garrote, 2015). However, climate variability and its extremes is fast becoming a serious concern to agricultural and socio-economic development (Poonia *et al.*, 2021).

Efforts geared towards mitigating climate change impact include agronomic management

strategies comprising soil conservation measure (e.g. zero tillage and minimum tillage) for increase in water use efficiency, cultivar selection and breeding for shorter life cycle, less impact on phenophases, drought tolerance etc., and changes in sowing time (Zhang and Lin, 2016, Luo *et al.*, 2018). Strzepek and Boehlert (2010) and Zhang and Lin (2016) also identified increasing water demands for municipal and industrial water use as part of the competition for reducing water resources in the face of climate change. Iglesias and Garrote (2015), therefore made case for multi-sectoral (financial, rural development, trade, industry and environment) approach in evolving adaption of water for agriculture in the face of climate change.

Restrictions by climate and Covid-19 within multi-sectoral context:

Although there may be benefit in certain geographical areas (Iglesias and Garrote, 2015; Auci and Vignani, 2021), climate variability or climate change impact, overall, tends towards high temperature, drop in total rainfall and scarcity of water with attendant decrease in cultivable area. Climate change can alter moisture condition in soil profile due to spatio-temporal variability of meteorological variables and this affect water management or hydrological component such as crop water requirement and crop irrigation requirement (Poonia *et al.*, 2021). Agricultural sector is known to be one of the most sensitive socio-economic sectors to climate variability, particularly, the rainfed crop production (e.g. wheat production in Australia, Luo *et al.*, 2018) and is known to depend mainly on water resources availability for crop irrigation (Auci and Vignani, 2021). Increase in evapotranspiration water demand, increase in percentage surface area under conditions of severe water stress (IPCC, 2014) and higher water demand due to warmer climate has been reported (Lobell *et al.*, 2013).

Socio-cultural concern is another factor that can be critical to achieving solution to climate change as it can clog the adoption of adaptation strategies including water-efficient technologies in relation to food production. Studies have shown that in the short terms, social barriers may limit the adoption of low cost and technically feasible measures in addressing and adapting to water-related challenges due to climate change (Quevauviller *et al.*, 2005; Iglesias and Garrote, 2015). Crop variety, disease, pest, climate change, water shortage and soil fertility have also been recognized as crucial to feeding expanding world population (Godfray *et al.* 2010; Mittler and Blumwald, 2010; Ray *et al.*, 2013; Ranjan *et al.*, 2019). Crop type selection is also one of the factors playing critical role in crop production and adaptation to challenges (e.g. water resources and yield reduction) posed by climate change. Increasing crop type that are more adaptable to local climatic condition in the face of climate change has also been encouraged (e.g. wheat production is suggested in Kansas, Zhang and Lin, 2016). While reporting crop rotation, tillage along with irrigation as agronomic practices that affect maize production in dry period in Germany, Huynh *et al.* (2019), ranked irrigation as the most important factor that

increased yields in sandy soils compared with the other two.

The need for irrigation and the associated challenges:

Irrigation is crucial for crop production, particularly, in arid climate where precipitation is negligible throughout the growing season and agriculture is irrigation-dependent (Salama, 2020). Irrigated lands accounts for 40% of global food production and expansion of agriculture-based economies is linked to the use of water for irrigation (WWAP, 2009). Projected increase in water requirement due to alteration in patterns of rainfall and temperature has attendant increase or change in the demand for crop irrigation (UNESCO, 2020; Poonia *et al.*, 2021) yet decreasing yields (Zhang and Lin, 2016) and quality of many crop products (Auci and Vignani, 2021). Based on predictions using climatic and hydrological models, the rise in temperature and evapotranspiration and changes in rainfall, due to climate change, will lead to decrease in rainfed crop yields. Yield increase has also been associated with irrigation (Ranjan *et al.*, 2019). Base on the prediction, another study indicated that exception to decline in crop yields will occur only if the agronomic and horticultural crop are irrigated with groundwater because irrigation by groundwater is usually constant and is not dependent on climate-susceptible precipitation and surface water (Shahvari *et al.*, 2019). Huynh *et al.* (2019) viewed irrigation as having potential to reduce annual yield fluctuations and their work showed that irrigation together with plow tillage and crop rotations can actually supports stable maize yields. This appears a solution in addressing the twin challenge of climate change and Covid-19 limitation to food production. Availability and steady supply of water needed for crop physiological requirement can reduce the sudden shock due to unexpected dry spell that is associated with climate change; thus, helping to maintain expected yields. In similar manner, with irrigation, stability in yield can be guaranteed if multiple cycles of production are adopted to close food production and supply gaps, and associated socio-economic problems (e.g. hunger, food inflation etc.) created by lockdown caused by Covid-19 pandemic.

There is challenge in water demand created by global warming (UNESCO, 2020) and water withdrawals due to irrigation. Yet irrigation is projected to increase by 5.5% by Food and

Agriculture Organisation between 2008 and 2050 (FAO, 2011). Efforts are being ramped up to address issues with water shortages arising from irrigation, climate change etc. Mahmoud *et al.* (2021) reported a simulated yield increase in maize and in yield of wheat using evenly irrigation gifts with controlled drainage despite 14% reduction in irrigation in El-Baradi area in the Nile Delta. In tackling drought in Kansas, an extreme weather condition that may be induced by climate change, Zhang and Lin (2016), advocated for high-efficiency irrigation infrastructure.

Irrigation types:

Different irrigations are practiced depending on location, availability of water and economic feasibility. These include surface irrigation where water is distributed on soil surface often without the use of mechanical pumps; sprinkler irrigation with water being distributed through overhead high-pressure sprinklers; manual irrigation through the use of watering cans; center pivot system with water being distributed through a set of sprinklers mounted on a wheel tower in circular motion; drip irrigation system where drops of water are delivered near plant roots thus reducing evaporation; and sub-irrigation where water table is raised through a system of pumping stations, ditches and canals.

The principle of capillary irrigation system:

The device is a sub-irrigation system. An artificial water table is created with PVC pipes filled with water serving as water reservoir through which water is transported by capillarity through a node directly to the plant root zone. Water transport from the reservoir through the water conducting medium in the node to the soil is based on potential gradient between the inlet (the node immersed in the reservoir) and the outlet (the end linked to the soil the device is irrigating). The water potential at the outlet is influenced by the evapotranspirative demand from the irrigated soil and the crop growing on it. The matric potential is the dominant driving force in this case bringing in the concept of capillarity (the reason it is also named a capillary irrigation system) within the soil pore and adsorption to soil solid. The pressure potential of the water in the reservoir together with the surface tension and critical angle of the water drives the water through the pores of the conducting medium in the node to the overlying soil in response to lower energy (primarily matric potential) created by the evapotranspirative demand.

The need for capillary irrigation:

Alterations in climate have serious implication on water resources including surface water amongst others (Azamzadeh *et al.*, 2013) while EEA (2012) and Shahvari *et al.* (2019) predicted severe shortage in irrigation and call for urgent plus future planning in water use. A call has been made to both save and conserve water resources through water resources management that is driven by demand (EEA, 2009). It aims to have more crops produced with less water through improvement in irrigation technologies, soil management and plant improvement, use of wastewater, right water pricing as caution to stimulate efficient water use and farmers' capacity building in water management (Chartzoulakis and Bertaki, 2015). As coping strategy for water scarcity due to climate change, adoption of water conservation and water saving and efficient technologies is increasing (Pronti *et al.*, 2020, Auci and Vignani, 2021). In tackling drought in Kansas, an extreme weather condition that may be induced by climate change, Zhang and Lin (2016), advocated for high-efficiency irrigation infrastructure. Auci and Vignani (2021) also made a call for incentivizing good practices on water irrigation management because human population and climate variability puts pressure on intensification of use of irrigation practices with attendant impact on- and scarcity- of water reservoir. A case has also been made for ease of handling, cost implication and water-efficient water management system along with soil conservation in addressing climate change-induced water challenges (Iglesias and Garrote, 2015). Efficient water use for crop production can be addressed using capillary irrigations system because water is drawn based on crop demand from the device.

This review discussed comparative evaluation of a novel capillary irrigation device developed by IDRC-MICROVEG Project team at Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile Ife, Nigeria in response to solving water shortages experienced by women vegetable farmers in southwestern parts of Nigeria (Adebooye *et al.* 2018). Studies were conducted in both the humid rainforest and humid savannah agro-ecosystems of southern Nigeria where the device was compared under the same conditions with manual sprinkler used by the farmers.

Yield of Amaranth in Response to Irrigation and Method of Fertilizer Application:

As shown in Fig 1, the yield of Amaranth was higher in capillary irrigation (T1) than sprinkler (T2) and

farmer's practice (T3) in both humid forest and humid savanna locations. The yield from capillary irrigation was consistently higher than sprinkler irrigation and farmer's practice all through first, second and third harvests, an evidence that the difference between productivities of each T1, T2 and T3 is not by chance but truly in response to irrigation and method of fertilizer application. This is despite the application of the same fertilizer rate in T1 and T2, and doubling the rate in T3. This result showed that not only methods and amount of fertilizer applied but also the irrigation method was important for the yield obtained from the Amaranth production, thus corroborating Qi *et al.* (2020) who reported that responses of maize to N fertilizer was influenced by level of water supplied. Li *et al.* (2020) also observed that grain and biomass yield of maize respond positively to nitrogen fertilizer only under adequately watered soil condition.

Moreover, more nutrient was probably available for the vegetable's growth from T1 than in T2, and T3. This was because in capillary irrigation, the fertilizer was applied by fertigation, hence there was high possibility of reduction of nutrient loss by

runoff and volatilization. However, in T2 and T3, the broadcast method used for the fertilizer application could have resulted in a lot of wastages through nutrient wash off from the plots by runoff generated during both sprinkler irrigation and farmers' conventional method of fertilizer application and irrigation practice. Another means of nutrient loss in T2 and T3 could be by volatilization of broadcast fertilizer. This result also showed a cumulative yield of 9.04, 7.50 and 8.23 Kg/6m² in T1, T2 and T3 respectively for humid forest location and 8.25, 6.32, 6.56 Kg/6m² for T1, T2, T3 in that order in humid savanna. This represents a yield increase of 20.5% and 30.5% in capillary irrigation over sprinkler irrigation in humid forest and humid savanna despite applying the same fertilizer amount. Similarly, a yield reduction of 9.8% and 25.7% was obtained from T1 over T3 in humid forest and humid savanna, even with doubling the fertilizer rates applied in T3.

Fig 1: Yield of amaranth in response to irrigation and methods of fertilizer application in (a) humid forest and (b) humid savanna locations (Adapted from Egbebi, 2021).

Water Application Efficiency, Water use Efficiency and Greenness Index of Amaranth in Response to the Irrigation Methods:

With equal volume of water applied in each of the irrigation method, Water Application Efficiency (WAE) compared the effectiveness of each of the irrigation methods to support water retention in crop

root zone. The WAE was not significantly different in T2 and T3 but a significantly higher value was obtained in T1 in humid forest location (Table 1). Similarly, T1 recorded the highest WAE in humid savanna zone.

Capillary irrigation only made water available at the crop root zone based on the crop evapotranspiration

demand and as a result, wastage from the soil was greatly reduced. On the other hand, losses of water to evaporation before infiltration, percolation beyond crop root zone and runoff, are valid means through which significant amount of water could be lost from sprinkler irrigation and farmer's practice.

Thus, the form and method of irrigation allow for differences in WAE as suggested by Table 1 under discussion. This fact of differences in variables that can influence WAE informs the estimation of different WAE for each irrigation method (Howell, 2003).

Table 1: Mean water application efficiency (WAE), Water use efficiency (WUE) and Greenness Index (GNI) of amaranth in response to irrigation in (a) humid forest and (b) humid savanna locations during the growing seasons of 2016-2017

Treatments	Humid Forest			Derived Savanna		
	WAE	WUE	GNI	WAE	WUE	GNI
Capillary Irrigation	6.93a	8.97a	52.26a	9.58a	5.54a	59.09a
Sprinkler Irrigation	6.24b	6.32b	40.85b	8.75b	4.19b	52.9b
Farmers Practice	6.40b	6.69b	41.77b	8.19c	3.41c	49.8b

Adapted from Egbebi (2021)

However, for the purpose of comparison, this study showed that T1 was more efficient in water management. This can be valuable during period of changing climate characterized by incessant dry spells, and acceleration and enhancement of production seasons to alleviate limitation in crop production during Covid-19 restriction. This appears a valuable contribution to efforts in developing water efficient technologies globally. For instance, Silva *et al.* (2013) reported higher water application efficiency with high water discharge rate and few crops when he experimented with a set of micro-sprinklers under banana cultivation in Brazil. This was probably because micro-sprinklers discharge water at a rate the minimized water loss by runoff. In the same pattern with WAE, Water Use Efficiency (WUE) of T1 was significantly higher than T2 and T3 in both locations of the study but unlike in humid forest, sprinkler irrigation had higher WUE than farmers' practice in humid savanna. Similarly, losses as a result of runoff, deep percolation and evaporation of applied water before infiltration were probably responsible for lower WUE in sprinkler irrigation and farmer's practice compared to capillary irrigation. In capillary irrigation on the other hand, losses were

minimal, hence more water was available to meet the crop evapotranspiration demand and produce higher biomass of the amaranth vegetable.

Highest greenness index was observed in capillary irrigation in both humid forest and savanna and this reflected the effectiveness of fertilizer applied by fertigation in capillary irrigation water compared to broadcast under sprinkler irrigation and farmers' practice. The greenness index was a response to amount of nutrient N availability for the vegetable. This was because nitrogen has been found to be involved in chlorophyll formation (Marenco and Lopes, 2009). Highest greenness index in capillary irrigation suggested that more nitrogen was taken up by crops under the irrigation system in line with Leonardo *et al.* (2013) and Ida *et al.* (2020) who in separate studies observed that chlorophyll index increased with urea fertilizer rates. This reflected the effectiveness of the irrigation methods in enhancing the Amaranth's accessibility and uptake of nitrogen.

Effect of Method of Irrigation on Water Required to Produce One Kilogram of Fresh Amaranth Vegetable:

The specific volume of water required to produce

one kilogram of fresh Amaranth under the different irrigation methods is shown in Table 2. Significantly highest volume of water was used to produce a kilogram of the vegetable under farmer's practice while capillary irrigation required the lowest water volume across the two agroecological zones during both dry and wet seasons. The study showed that less than half of water volume required to produce a kilogram of vegetable under farmers' practice was used in capillary irrigation in the humid forest. Similarly, the differences in water volume required per kilogram of Amaranth among the irrigation methods was large in humid savanna. It could also be observed that higher volume of water was needed per kilogram of fresh vegetable during the dry

season than in the wet, and unfortunately, water availability was always limited during this period. With capillary irrigation, farmers would have conserved 138.61 and 120.78 Litres of water in humid forest and humid savanna, respectively, than with farmers' conventional method of irrigation. Sprinkler irrigation saved 118.02 and 69.7 Litres of water in humid forest and savanna in same study. Water are increasingly being adjudged a scarce resource and hence challenge the capacity of nations and communities in meeting their food demand (Rijsberman, 2006; Hanjra and Qureshi, 2010) and with current erratic rainfall in Nigeria, a water saving irrigation method is desirable to mitigate water scarcity.

Table 2: Effects of method of irrigation on volume of water (Litres) required to produce a kg of fresh *Amaranthus viridis* under two agroecological zones in Nigeria

Treatments	Humid Forest		Derived Savanna	
	Wet Season	Dry Season	Wet Season	Dry Season
Capillary Irrigation	56.25c	117.43c	85.36c	205.83c
Sprinkler Irrigation	94.26b	138.02b	123.85b	256.91b
Farmers Practice	125.25a	256.04a	134.86a	326.61a

Adapted from Egbebi (2021)

More importantly, it can be seen in Figure 1 that with the least water use under capillary irrigation, more yield was recorded than each of the other method of irrigation with the same or even higher fertilizer rate applied. The reason follows the effectiveness of water delivery of each of the irrigation methods as it showed that loss of water to runoff, deep percolation, seepage and evaporation were probably more in farmers' practice and sprinkler than in capillary. This was in line with Stanslaus *et al.* (2018) who concluded that it was possible to obtain higher yield of rice with relatively lower volume of water when a more efficient irrigation technology is deployed.

Effect of Irrigation Method Nitrogen Use Efficiency

The nitrogen use efficiency (Table 3) of Amaranth under capillary irrigation was significantly higher than what was observed under sprinkler irrigation in humid forest location in the study. However, no

statistically significant difference was noticed in nitrogen use efficiency of the vegetable under the two irrigation methods in humid savanna. Similar to earlier submission on WAE and WAE, higher NUE can be linked to reduction of irrigation water wastage and subsequent availability of more N for uptake in capillary compared to sprinkler irrigation. Therefore, higher NUE in capillary irrigation is an indication of higher N economy than in sprinkler, in which leaching of N, and loses as result of runoff and volatilization were likely more prominent. With this work higher NUE and a likely reduction in environmental contamination equally addressed by Agostini *et al.* (2010) and Rahn (2002) realized under low N rate was obtained under capillary irrigation system in humid forest. Moreover, difference in method of fertilizer application as observed by Linaje *et al.* (2005), Ma and Kalb (2006) as well as simultaneous management of water and fertilizer by fertigation observed by Battilani *et al.* (2003) and Singandhupe *et al.* (2003)

could also be responsible for the difference in NUE between the two methods used in the application of fertilizer. On the other hand, result obtained in humid savanna indicated that NUE was not different between the two methods of irrigation. The similarity in NUE between the two irrigation methods contrary to the result from humid savanna may be as a result of possible environmental factors such as soil fertility and weather condition such as rainfall. There would not be any significant

variation in NUE if the soil in this location was very fertile. Even Xiukang and Yingying (2016) noted that application of nitrogen fertilizer without giving consideration to the residual soil N might result in low yield and hence low NUE. This was because under sufficient and available N, the nutrient would not be a limiting factor to biomass yield as opposed to an N-deficient situation. Subsequently, unabsorbed N would be leached during heavy rainfall and irrigation.

Table 3: Effects of irrigation type on nitrogen use efficiency of *Amaranthus viridis* in two agroecological zones on Nigeria

Treatments	Humid Forest	Derived Savanna
	Nitrogen use efficiency	
Capillary Irrigation	21.61a	19.96a
Sprinkler Irrigation	16.36b	23.48a

Adapted from Kuye (2019)

Conclusion

The paper advocates efficient water management through irrigation in the face of challenges posed by climate change and potential of efficient irrigation technology to accelerate food production. Field

capillary irrigation system was found to improve both water application efficiency and water use efficiency of Amaranth, and increase the yield of the vegetable from 20 – 30% in humid forest and humid savanna, respectively.

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